
EFFECTS OF ACADEMIC SELF-EFFICACY AND ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION ON MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN UYO METROPOLIS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination and of secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics in Uyo Metropolis. Three research questions guided the study while three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. This study adopted a correlation survey research design. The study is carried out in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of all the 6,840 senior secondary year two (SS₂) students across 34 registered secondary schools in Uyo. A sample of 420 SS₂ students was used in this study using a multi-stage sampling technique. The Self-Efficacy Scale (SES) was adopted while the Tuckman Procrastination Scale (TPS) was adopted by the researcher. The academic achievement was measured by Mathematics examination scores derived from SS₂ students' termly results for the 2022/2023 academic session. The TPS was an adapted instrument and therefore subjected to face validation by three experts. A pilot test was given on the TPS questionnaire using 20 students from a public secondary school in Abak Local Government Area and a coefficient of 0.83 was obtained. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to answer the research questions while t-test and F-test were used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The finding revealed that the low positive relationship between academic self-efficacy scores and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics is

significant. The findings also revealed that the low negative relationship between academic procrastination scores and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics is significant. Finally, the study found a significant joint relationship between academic self-efficacy, academic procrastination, and Mathematics achievement. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that school counsellors should employ creative strategies to help learners develop high self-belief and manage their time precisely to improve academic outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

The scientific and technological development of any nation depends on the efforts made by such nation to advance her students learning of mathematics and other mathematical sciences (Wonu & Arokoyu 2016). Mathematics is made a compulsory subject throughout primary and secondary school in Nigeria, which has in turn helped in the advancement of the nation. Despite the central role of numeracy in different contexts and everyday situations, children's underachievement in mathematics remains a consistent and significant problem (Dowker, 2004). Uyo, the capital of Akwa Ibom State, has a growing population of secondary school students, but local research has yet to fully examine the systemic challenges and psychological variables that shape their academic outcomes. Among these variables, mathematics anxiety and academic self-efficacy have emerged as central constructs in international literature on student motivation and behavior (Ashcraft, 2002).

Procrastination is the deferral or avoidance of an action or task to a later to a late time (Kumari et al., 2018). Although it occurs in various areas, it is most commonly associated with education and work, due to external and specific deadlines set for the completion of a task or a job (Klingsieck, 2013). Psychologists interested in mechanisms of growth and change have traditionally been concerned with such self-regulating processes of course, substantial contributions are made by external agents, but even without external pressure human thinkers play with thinking (Gardener, 1978).

Procrastination clearly has an adverse effect on academic functioning, including achievement. However, less is known about the potential reverse effects of academic achievement on procrastination, as well as other factors that may explain students' tendency to procrastinate. Academic Procrastination has received many empirical attentions especially within the field of psychology. Research findings have generally linked procrastination to personal behavioural factors such as lack of motivation, deficiencies in self-regulation, external locus of control, perfectionism, disorganization and poor time management (Olaniyi, 2019). Self-efficacy refers to students' belief whether they are able to achieve desired outcome (Bandura, 1977b). It determines future behavior, the amount of effort that people will invest in certain situations, as well as the choices of activities and perseverance in coping with difficulties, which further affect the outcome of a certain behavior (Kurtovic et al., 2019). Operationally, self-efficacy defines a child's belief (personal conviction) that they can successfully achieve at a designated level on an academic task or attain a specific academic goal (Nwadinobsi et al., 2023). There are series of examinations such as the Common Entrance Examination (CEE), First School Leaving Certificate Examination (FSLCE), Junior Secondary School Certificate Examination (JSSCE), Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE), Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME), and a host of others play a dramatic role in the lives of students (Nwadinobsi et al., 2023). These high-stakes examinations are critical because they determine students' progression to higher education and entry into prestigious careers. Academic achievement in teaching-learning means the attainment of set of objectives of instruction (Uwakele & Okoli, 2019). It is the optimal requirement that shows that a student have positively assimilated what have been taught in a learning process.

Statement of The Problem

Academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination are things that really affect how well students do in school. Even though a lot of research has been done on these things there is still no information about how they

affect student achievement in Uyo. We can see this because students are not doing well in exams especially in English Language and Mathematics (WAEC, 2024). When the researcher decided to look into this, it was found that teachers get frustrated because students often put off doing their schoolwork. This means that students delay giving in their notes to be marked and they do not do their assignments on time. They only study for tests at the last minute even when teachers remind them to start early. When we talked to teachers they told us that academic procrastination and self-efficacy are problems in secondary schools all over Uyo. A lot of students do not think they can do well in exams, mostly because they do not know how to study. They do not prepare well, which often leads to bad grades.

Also other studies have shown that there is a connection between procrastination and self-efficacy but the results are different depending on the level of study. Some people have looked at how these things affect achievement but not many people have looked at how academic procrastination and self-efficacy together affect how well secondary school students do in important subjects, like English Language and Mathematics. This study is trying to fill that gap and learn more about self-efficacy and academic procrastination.

Purpose of The Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination as correlates of secondary school students' academic achievement in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The relationship between academic self-efficacy and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics.
2. The relationship between academic procrastination and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics.
3. The joint relationship between academic self-efficacy and procrastination in secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What type of relationship exists between academic self-efficacy scores and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics?
2. What type of relationship exists between academic procrastination scores and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics?
3. What type of relationship jointly exists between the self-efficacy scores and academic procrastination scores and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between academic self-efficacy scores and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between academic procrastination scores and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics.

H₀₃: There is no significant joint relationship between academic self-efficacy scores and academic procrastination scores with secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Framework

The word Self-efficacy was first used by Albert Bandura in 1977. Since then, this area has been growing steadily in many aspects of human endeavour. Academic Self-efficacy means Self confidence, Self reliance and trust in oneself (Sharma & Nasa, 2014). It is concerned with how well a person believes he or she will be able to reach a desired outcome in a designated area (Bandura, 1977b). In Education, Self-efficacy is a key contributing factor to learner's success, because self-efficacy influences the choices learners make and the courses of action, they pursue (Pajares, 1996). Academic Self-efficacy refers to how positive people think and act towards academic tasks. Academic Self-efficacy refers to students'

perceptions or their competence to do their classwork (Midgley et. al 2000). Academic Self-efficacy is necessary for a boost in the positive outcome of students' academic pursuit. Procrastination as given by the Cambridge Dictionary (2025) is the act of delaying something that must be done often because it is unpleasant or boring. Procrastination refers to delaying tasks despite expecting to be worse off for the day (Steel 2007).

Academic Procrastination means habitually delaying work with academic task to the extent that the delays become detrimental to performance, wellbeing and health (Svartdal & Løkke 2022). Conservative estimates indicate a prevalence of at least 50%, suggesting that a half or more of all students habitually procrastinate tasks such as reading before tests and exams and preparing assignments (Pychyl et al 2000) Academic achievement is commonly understood as the success individuals attain in educational settings, typically assessed through grades and test scores that reflect the fulfillment of academic goals set by students, teachers, or educational institutions (EBSCO, 2025). Academic achievement gives some level of satisfaction to the individual(s) who attain such level.

Theoretical Framework

Social Cognitive Theory is a psychological theory that emphasizes how people learn by observing others, a process known as observational learning (McLeod & Guy-Evans 2025). The theory was propounded by Albert Bandura in 1977. The theory posits that all behaviour is learned through observation and focuses on how people perceive and respond to their immediate social surroundings. Within this framework, self-efficacy serves as a mediating variable that mediates engagement and persistence. Where an individual with low self-efficacy repeatedly encounters failure in mathematics, can generate anxiety which promotes avoidant behaviour such as procrastination. On the other hand, Temporal Motivation Theory (TMT) is described as one of the more comprehensive and promising theories equipped to further our understanding of procrastination (Lord et al., 2010; Schmidt et al., 2013). Temporal Motivation Theory (TMT) is an integrative framework developed by Piers Steel and Cornelius Konig in

2006. The theory proposes that motivation is dynamic state that varies over time depending on the perceived value of the task, confidence in success and how soon the reward or outcome will be realized (Bumgarner et al., 2025). The theory is formalized with a mathematical model that predicts the strength of motivation based on four variables given by:

$$\text{Motivation} = \frac{\text{Expectancy} \times \text{Value}}{\text{Impulsiveness} \times \text{Delay}}$$

In this model, low self-efficacy reduces expectancy, which reduces motivation to initiate or sustain academic tasks, resulting in procrastination.

Empirical Framework

Several studies have been made to show correlation between self-efficacy and procrastination. Hen and Goroshit (2014) investigated the relationship between emotional intelligence, academic self-efficacy, academic performance and academic procrastination in higher education. They used a sample of 287 Israeli college students using a convenience sampling. The data was analyzed by structural equation modeling analysis using AMOS. They found out that emotional intelligence has a negative indirect effect on academic procrastination and positive indirect effect on academic performance. Also, a study carried out by Nwadinobsi et. al (2023) investigated academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination as correlates of secondary school students' academic achievement in Anambra State, Nigeria. Using a sample of 1800 SS2 students from a population of 6396, the researcher adopted the Self-Efficacy Scale (SES) and Tuckman Procrastination Scale (TPS) was used as data collection instruments. Pearson Product Moment was used to answer the research questions, while t-test of correlational analysis was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The finding reveals that the positive relationship between academic self-efficacy scores and secondary school students' academic achievement in English Language and Mathematics is significant. Also the findings revealed that the negative relationship between academic procrastination scores and

secondary school students' academic achievement in English and Mathematics is significant.

A study carried out by Kurtovic et. al (2019) examined the relations of academic achievement, self-efficacy and perfectionism with procrastination in university students and to examine whether procrastination can be predicted by academic achievement, self-efficacy and perfectionism dimensions. 227 university students completed the Tuckman Procrastination Scale, Almost Perfect Scale (APS) and General Self-Efficacy Scale. Results from this study revealed negative correlations of academic achievement, self-efficacy and adaptive perfectionism with procrastination, and a positive correlation between maladaptive perfectionism and procrastination. Therefore, this reviewed literature reveals evidence of the effect of low self-efficacy and procrastination on academic achievement of students. This study aims to expand this evidence base in Uyo Metropolis.

METHODOLOGY

Correlational survey research design was used in this study. The research was conducted in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The population comprised all 6,840 Senior Secondary Two (SS2) students across the 34 registered secondary schools in Uyo. From this population, a sample of 420 SS2 students was selected using a multi-stage sampling technique. Two standardized instruments were utilized: the Self-Efficacy Scale (SES) and the Tuckman Procrastination Scale (TPS), the latter adapted by the researcher. Academic achievement was measured using students' Mathematics examination scores obtained from their SS2 termly results for the 2022/2023 academic session. Since the TPS was adapted, it was subjected to face validation by three experts. A pilot test was carried out with 20 students from a public secondary school in Abak Local Government Area. The pilot test yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.83, which indicated a good internal consistency. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used in answering the research

questions, while t-test and F-test were used to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 alpha level.

Results

Table 1: Pearson (r) on academic self-efficacy scores and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics

Sources of variance	N	Academic self-efficacy scores (r)	Mathematics (r)	Remark
Academic self-efficacy scores	420	1.00	0.36	Low positive relationship
Mathematics	420	0.36	1.00	

Table 1 shows that there is a low positive relationship of 0.36 existing between academic self-efficacy scores and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics.

Table 2: Pearson (r) on academic procrastination scores and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics

Sources of variance	N	Academic procrastination scores (r)	Mathematics (r)	Remark
Academic procrastination scores	420	1.00	-0.39	Low negative relationship
Mathematics	420	-0.39	1.00	

Table 2 shows that there is a low negative relationship of -0.39 existing between academic procrastination scores and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics.

Table 3: Multiple Regression Analysis on the joint relationship between academic self-efficacy, academic procrastination, and Mathematics achievement

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.64	0.41	0.40	11.23

Table 3 shows that the joint relationship between academic self-efficacy, academic procrastination, and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics is 0.64. The coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.41 indicates that both variables jointly account for 41% of the variance in Mathematics achievement.

Table 4: t-test on the significance of Pearson r of academic self-efficacy and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics

N	Cal. r	df	Cal. t	p-value	Remark
420	0.36	418	11.04	0.000	Significant

Table 4 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance, the p-value 0.000 is less than 0.05; therefore, the first null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 5: t-test on the significance of Pearson r of academic procrastination and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics

N	Cal. r	df	Cal. t	p-value	Remark
420	-0.39	418	5.89	0.000	Significant

Table 5 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance, the p-value 0.000 is less than 0.05; therefore, the second null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 6: ANOVA on the significance of the joint relationship

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	36442.34	2	18221.17	144.62	.000
Residual	52538.16	417	125.99		
Total	88980.50	419			

Table 6 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance, the F-value 144.62 is significant at $p=0.000$; thus, the third null hypothesis is rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings revealed a low positive relationship between academic self-efficacy and Mathematics achievement, which is significant. This aligns with Hen and Goroshit (2014), who found that emotional intelligence has a positive indirect effect on academic performance through self-efficacy, suggesting that students' belief in their own capabilities plays a meaningful role in driving Mathematics success. This finding also the same as that of Nwadinobsi et al. (2023), who reported a significant positive relationship between academic self-efficacy scores and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics in Anambra State. Furthermore, the findings revealed a low negative relationship between academic procrastination and Mathematics achievement, which is significant. This aligns with Kurtovic et al. (2019), who found negative correlations between academic achievement, self-efficacy and procrastination, indicating that students who consistently delay academic tasks tend to record lower performance outcomes. Similarly, Nwadinobsi et al. (2023) reported a significant negative relationship between academic procrastination scores and secondary school students' academic achievement in Mathematics, further reinforcing this finding in the Nigerian secondary school context.

Also, the study revealed a significant joint relationship between academic self-efficacy, academic procrastination, and secondary school students' Mathematics achievement, with both variables jointly accounting for 41% of the variance in achievement. This is consistent with Hen and Goroshit (2014), who demonstrated that self-efficacy mediates the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance, and with Kurtovic et al. (2019), whose structural model confirmed that self-efficacy and procrastination together predict academic achievement. The joint predictive power observed in this study reinforces the argument that interventions targeting both constructs simultaneously are likely to yield greater improvements in students' Mathematics performance.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it is concluded that the low positive relationship of academic self-efficacy and the low negative relationship of academic procrastination with Mathematics achievement are both significant. Collectively, these constructs significantly predict the academic achievement of secondary school students in Uyo Metropolis. In simple terms, students who believe in themselves tend to do a little better in Mathematics. Students who delay their work tend to do worse. Both factors together explain 41% of why some students succeed in Mathematics while others struggle. This shows that self-efficacy and procrastination work together, not separately.

RECOMMENDATION

Recommendations Based on what the researcher found out from this study, here are some suggestions:

1. Schools should help students feel more confident in Mathematics: Students who believe in themselves do better so teachers and school counselors should make sure the classroom is a place where students feel encouraged not discouraged. They can do this by celebrating wins giving helpful feedback and using examples that students can relate to.

2. Teachers should find ways to help students stop putting things off: Students who delay studying usually do poorly. Teachers can break down Mathematics tasks into steps and give students regular short deadlines instead of just one big exam. This makes the subject feel less scary and harder to avoid.
3. School counselors should create programs that deal with both confidence and procrastination: Since both of these things together explained a lot of why students do poorly in Mathematics it's better to deal with them at the same time. Counseling sessions, workshops or student support programs should help students believe in themselves and manage their tasks better.
4. Parents should help their children develop study habits at home: Procrastination often starts at home. So parents should learn how to encourage their children to study check their homework and motivate them without putting too much pressure on them.
5. Other researchers need to do research on this topic in different subjects and areas: This study was about Mathematics in one place, but similar things might be true for other subjects and parts of Nigeria. Future researchers should investigate these relationships in different contexts to help make better decisions about education, in Nigeria.

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